

Permeability Modeling for BD Fabric

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ICCM24

- At CRC, R&DE(ENGRS)-
 - Focus on large and load bearing primary composites structures
 - Out-of-Autoclave processes
 - VARTM
 - RFI-Resin Film Infusion

Composites Bridge

Composite Dome Structure

- Process Design- Liquid Injection Molding Simulation (LIMS) Software
- Mostly glass and carbon fabrics
- Double curvature structure: mostly used BD fabrics for ease of draping
- BD fabrics: Complex architecture
- Main issue in process modeling- Prediction of fabric wetting and saturation times

- BD fabric ply architecture
 - Fiber tows in both in-plane directions
 - Inter-tow gaps in in-plane directions
- Terminology
 - Warp tows and Warp inter-tow gaps
 - Weft tows and weft inter-tow gaps
- Fabric porosity-Non-uniform
 - Inter-tow gaps-larger as compared to above-Order~ 10^{-1} mm.
 - Tows –lower inter-filament distances-Order~ 10^{-2} mm to 10^{-3} mm

BD stitched glass fabric ply

Schematic

BD stitched glass fabric ply- Weft sublayer

- Flow front lag between inter-tow gap and tows
- Flow-Two length scales- w.r.t Fabric ply
 - Tow-micro-level flow
 - Inter-tow-Macro level flow
- Nature - Dual scale flow
- In-plane flow characteristics-Saturation region and Partially saturated region^{1, 2}
- Partially saturation region bounded by
 - Saturated flow front-Warp and Weft tows and inter-tow gaps
 - Wetting flow front-Inter-tow gap

- Terminology
 - Warp tows and Warp inter-tow gaps
 - Weft tows and weft inter-tow gaps
- u = Point-wise axial velocity in inter-tow gap
- v = Point-wise transverse velocity in inter-tow gap
- p = Point-wise pressure and p_s = pressure at $x = 0$
- \dot{s}_z = sink rate in weft tow (1/s)
- φ_{tf} = Tow porosity
- $V_{tow-plywf}$ = Weft tow fraction
- \bar{v} = Volume-averaged transverse velocity in warp tows
- $K_{yytow} = K_{zztow}$ = Transverse tow permeability
- L_{ps} = Length of partially saturated region

Approach

- Domain analysis-Start of partially saturated region till end of inter-tow gap flow front
- Constant pressure face injection in y - z plane and flow direction in Warp
- Considering middle ply analysis
- Some Important Assumptions
 - Layers perfectly aligned
 - Warp and Weft tow infusion- only from warp inter-tow gap^{1, 2, 3}
 - Tow impregnation-Constant pressure on interface
 - Tow shape-Rectangular
 - Sink rate a function of x -coordinate only

¹ Pavel et al. Poly. Comp. 2010

² Binetruy et al. Jour. Comp. Mat. 1998

³ Dungan et al. Jour. Comp. Mat. 2002

- Important observation
 - Warp tows continuously absorb fluid from warp gap
 - Weft tows discretely absorb fluid from warp gap

- Incompressible, viscous and Newtonian¹ flow: continuity equation

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = -\dot{s}_z \varphi_{tf} V_{tow-plywf} - (\varphi_{tf} V_{tow-plywf} x) \frac{\partial \dot{s}_z}{\partial x}$$

- Gap region-Stokes equation¹

$$-\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \mu \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} = 0$$

$$-\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \mu \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} = 0$$

- Cross-differentiating

$$\frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial y^3} - \frac{\partial^3 v}{\partial x^3} = 0$$

¹ Pavel et al. Poly. Comp. 1996

- Flow Assumptions-
 - Variation of u and v retained as polynomial
 - Boundary layer inside the warp porous tow-negligible-An implication of only transverse infusion of warp tows
 - No-slip boundary condition at interface between gap and warp tow¹
 - Capillary forces neglected
- At the most: Variation of $u = u(y^2)$ and $v = v(x^2)$
- Boundary conditions
 - At interface, $y=\pm h$, no-slip condition
 - For transverse velocity, $v = 0$ for tow saturation conditions at $x=0$ and L_{ps} .
- Variation of u, v -Depends on nature of pressure variation in inter-tow gap and is found out using LIMS
- BD fabric-modeled in LIMS- Using microstructure study of fabric

BD stitched glass fabric ply

¹ Binetruy et al. Comp Sci. Tech. 1997

Infusion of BD stitched 845 gsm glass fabric (Saertex make) with resin

SEM of a cured single layer BD stitched 845gsm glass fabric for measuring warp inter-tow gap

Measurement of filament radius which is in the range of 12-15 μm

SEM of the single layer with measurement of half tow thickness- 317 μm and ply thickness of 634 μm

Measurement of tow width that is equal to 2.921 mm

Transverse tow permeability (K_{yytow}) measurement with tow of BD stitched glass fabric

Nature of Pressure Variation in Inter-tow gap

Flow chart depicting scope of simulation studies in LIMS

- Considering middle ply analysis
- Nature of pressure variation-from LIMS simulations
- 3D FE modeling in LIMS for BD layup
- Fabric stitch not modeled
- Components of model depicting fabric unit cell
- Symmetry of fabric architecture and layup used
- Simulation done for inter-tow gap $2h=0.3$ mm- 0.5 mm
- Considering constant pressure face injection across yz -plane

Schematic of dual scale BD layup depicting symmetry along A-A plane and B-B plane

3D FE model showing details of fabric unit cell. Mesh for inter-tow gap in weft direction is purposely not shown for easy understanding of the model.

- Pressure variation along the length of the inter-tow gap can be considered as linear as a first approximation
- LIMS results show that for fabric like BD, pressure variation across the gap width can be considered as constant
- Linear pressure variation -Implications
 - Variation of u with respect to x is only due to fluid absorbed by weft tows
 - For a particular time step, pressure gradient is constant
 - Spatial variation of u is $u = u(y^2, x)$ and no coupling of xy term
- No Pressure variation across gap width-Implication
 - Spatial variation of v is $v = v(x)$ for a linear pressure variation along gap length

Pressure variation along the length of the warp inter-tow gap with a linear fit

Pressure variation across the width of the warp inter-tow gap

- Sink term for weft tow

$$s_z = \frac{V_R}{V_T} = \frac{z_f a}{h_t a} = \frac{z_f}{h_t}$$

- Following the approach of Fuping et al.¹ expression for \dot{s}_z

$$\dot{s}_z = \frac{K_{zzt\text{ow}}}{h_t^2 \mu \varphi_{tf}} \frac{p}{s_z}$$

- Net flow rate is given by

- $Q_{net} = udy - vdx - \dot{s}_z \varphi_{tf} v_t x dy$, Where, $\bar{v} = \frac{K_{yyt\text{ow}}}{\mu} \frac{P_s \left(1 - \frac{x}{L_f}\right)^{-P_f}}{a}$ and $u = \frac{1}{2\mu} \frac{dp}{dx} y^2 - \frac{h^2}{2\mu} \frac{dp}{dx}$

$$K_{effgap} = \frac{1}{h_{warp+a}} \left[\frac{h_{warp}^3}{3} \right] - K_{yyt\text{ow}} \frac{L_{ps}^2}{(h_{warp+a})a} - \frac{h_{warp}}{h_{warp+a}} \frac{K_{zzt\text{ow}}}{h_t^2} \left(1 - \frac{h_{weft}}{h_{weft+a}} \right) \frac{1}{\bar{s}_z} \left(\frac{L_{ps}^2}{6} \right)$$

Where, $\bar{s}_z = \frac{1}{L_{ps}} \int_0^{L_{ps}} s_z(x) dx$ - Average Weft tow saturation determined from simulations

- Input to the model

- Fabric architecture parameters
- Processing parameters- $\bar{s}_z, L_{ps}, K_{yyt\text{ow}}$

FE Simulation Results

- FE simulations- $2h=0.3$ mm, 0.4 mm and 0.5 mm
- L_{ps} smallest for $2h=0.3$ mm gap
- Gap fill time for $2h=0.3$ mm is more as compared to $2h=0.4$ mm and $2h=0.5$ mm

Weft tow saturation plot $2h=0.5$ mm gap

(a) Flow time contours (b) Fill time contours for $2h=0.5$ mm

- Fill time to fill warp gap noted
- Porosity: $\varphi = (\text{warp gap volume})/(\text{total volume})$
- $K_{effgap_LIMS} = \frac{\varphi\mu L^2}{2t_{LIMS}\Delta p'}$ Wetting permeability
- Effect of warp length on L_{ps} , K_{effgap_LIMS}

Permeability Model Predictions and Comparison with LIMS and Experiments

- For L_{ps} comparison, experimental value and simulation values are in close agreement
- Comparison of permeability values
 - Permeability values from LIMS are higher as compared to experimental values
 - Model values are in between experimental and simulation

UD flow experiment with un-sheared fabric-Single layer
Experimental value of L_{ps} = 15mm-20mm

Comparison of Model Results and LIMS Results

Experiment	Experimental	Simulation L_{ps}	Permeability	LIMS Result
al Result	L_{ps} (mm)	(mm)	Model Result	(m^2)
(m^2)			(m^2)	
3.39E-11	15-20	18.4	7.52E-11	4.86E-11

Comparison of Permeability Results

Conclusions and Future Work

- Conclusions

- Important parameters that characterize a flow in a dual-scale fabric are L_{ps} , and average weft tow saturation \bar{s}_z .
- Expression for effective permeability (wetting) that depends on parameters
 - Fabric architecture: $2h_{warp}$, $2h_{weft}$, tow width- a
 - Processing parameters: ply/tow thickness- h_t , K_{yytow} , \bar{s}_z and L_{ps}
- L_{ps} and $K_{effgap-LIMS}$ increases as $2h_{wa}$ increases
- For a sufficiently longer mold length or warp length of fabric, L_{ps} , \bar{s}_z , $K_{effgap-LIMS}$ remains constant

- Future Work

- Heterogeneity in thickness direction
- Tow shape- Elliptical and radial infusion of tow
- Application in fabric draping

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